

CLASSIFICATION AND GENERAL PROPERTIES OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS

KHUJANIYAZOV SHERJON BEKBOEVICH

Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

Annotation. In "Study of the structure of organic substances used as medicinal substances and the chemical bases of their effects", students can study: the composition, structure, reaction mechanisms of medicinal substances, the changes that occur as a result of their effects, and possible positive and negative effects. So, the student should be able to perform audio-visual work, i.e. listen to the lecture and record the necessary information, familiarize himself with the case, understand the textual media, be able to summarize the information, i.e. understand its function in the organism, be able to analyze the received information and finally determine the problem being studied.

Key words: problem situation, research, project method, case-study method

Introduction. "Study of the structure and properties of biologically active substances" and "Connecting the chemical structure of biologically active substances with their spatial structure" is required to provide students with in-depth knowledge in the study of substances that are found in the body and play an important role in its life activity. Proteins, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, lipids (fats) and other biologically active substances. The activity of these substances is determined by their structure. For example, in protein synthesis, since DNA carries information, m-RNA, t-RNA and r-RNA use the information in sequence to synthesize a new protein (for example, a new type of coronavirus, COVID-19). It is also possible to provide information to students in the direction of the 2nd issue.

It is important to understand the molecular level reactions of proteins, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, lipids, etc. found in living organisms in "Study of the structure of the substances involved in the metabolic process - proteins, carbohydrates, nucleic acids, lipids, etc. and their reactions at the molecular level." Because these substances are constantly broken down and synthesized in the process of metabolism in the organism. Studying the structure of these substances at the molecular level allows us to understand the mechanisms of their transformation and predict the changes that may occur later. So, the student will have to perform audio-visual work individually, that is, listen to the lecture and record the necessary information, get acquainted with the case, understand the textual media, be able to summarize the information, that is, understand its function in the body, be able to analyze the received information, and finally determine the problem being studied.

Step 2 (after class for lectures): Clarify the case and set the learning task is important for students. (8) questions in the discussed issues are educational tasks. Therefore, students can work individually or in a group (on the basis of textbooks, lecture texts or internet materials) to master these lectures. In this, the relevance of the problems is determined and a solution is sought, the main problem is determined, that is, the spatial structure of biologically active substances as a determinant of its activity.

Stage 3 (after the lesson for the lecture): Finding a solution to the educational task by analyzing the main problem in the case, developing ways to solve it. It is possible to work individually or in a group (based on a textbook, lecture text or internet materials) in a series of 8 questions. First, alternative solutions are developed, for example, bioregulators are studied on the Internet from the database of the following years. The possibilities and obstacles of solving each question are analyzed. For example, the study of the spatial structure of biologically active substances may not be adequately animated in textbooks

and lectures. To master this, animation materials and video materials will be necessary. These materials are available from the teacher and on the Internet.

Conclusion. In the higher education system, to establish close cooperation relations with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions in their fields, to introduce advanced foreign experiences into the educational process, especially to accelerate the work on training and upgrading the skills of promising pedagogues and scientific personnel in leading foreign scientific and educational institutions.

2. It is necessary for each higher medical educational institution to have a sufficient level of scientific and pedagogical potential, and it is appropriate to ensure that it meets the requirements of their awareness of the normative and legal documents being established;

3. Making wide use of foreign experiences in the training of pedagogues: increasing attention to the acquisition of knowledge about modular training, credit, the concept of rating, technology rules, principles, control process organization, interactive technologies and their effective use;

Literature

1. МАШАРИПОВ, ОО; БЕКЧАНОВ, БГ; „ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ, ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ Учредители: Олимп,9,,84-87,,
2. Нуралиев, НА; Бектимиров, АМТ; Рахманова, СС; Машарипов, О; Машарипов, ВУ; „Методические основы разработки иммуноферментной тест-системы на основе бактериальных антигенов, Методические рекомендации.-Ургенч,,,,,2006,
3. Машарипов, О; „Характеристика специфического антимикробного иммунитета при остром и хроническом тонзиллите,,,,,2012, автореф. дис.... кан. мед. наук Ташкент.

4. Машарипов, Отабой Олимович; ,Самые опасные глобальные инфекции на современном этапе,Вестник науки и образования,,5-1 (136),79-83,2023,ООО «Олимп»
5. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar; Rakhimova, Feroza; Sobirova, Sabokhat; Allaberganov, Odilbek; ,Mathematical Bases Of Parallel Algorithms For The Creation Of Medical Databases,InterConf,,,,2021,
6. Saidovich, Rakhimov Bakhtiyar; Bakhtiyarovich, Saidov Atabek; Farkhodovich, Babajanov Boburbek; Ugli, Karimov Doston Alisher; Qizi, Musaeva Mukhtasar Zayirjon; ,Analysis And Using of the Features Graphics Processors for Medical Problems,Texas Journal of Medical Science,7,,105-110,2022,
7. Rakhimov, Bakhtiyar Saidovich; Saidov, Atabek Bakhtiyarovich; Allayarova, Asal Akbarovna; ,Using the Model in Cuda and Opencl for Medical Signals,International Journal on Orange Technologies,4,10,84-86,2022,Research Parks Publishing
8. Рахимов, Бахтияр Саидович; Жуманиёзов, Сардор Пирназарович,Аппаратно-ориентированный алгоритм вычисления коэффициентов в базисах J-функций,Актуальные вопросы технических наук,,59-62,2015,
9. Касымов, СС; Зайнидинов, ХН; Рахимов, БС; ,Применение базисных сплайнов для предварительной обработки экспериментальных данных,"Тезисы докл. XVI-Международная научная конф., Санкт" ,,,2003,
10. Рахимов, БС; ,Проектирование спецпроцессов для обработки сигналов на основе матричной диаграммы занятости,Научно-технический журнал Ферганского политехнического института,4,,31,2003,

11. Рахимов, БС; , "Кусочно-полиномиальные методы на основе функций Уолша, Актуальные вопросы в области технических и социально-экономических наук", Межвузовский сб. научн. трудов. Ташкент, 1, 42, 2006,
12. Rakhimov, BS; Allabeganov, OR; Saidov, AB; , Processor means for the spectral analysis of medical signals on the of polynomial walsh bases epra, International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD), 5, 7, 10-11, 2020,